

Proposal for a ‘**Freshwater Eutrophication Index (FEI)**’ headline indicator under the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework

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Executive Summary

This proposal recommends the adoption of the Freshwater Eutrophication Index (FEI) as a headline indicator within the monitoring framework of the Kunming–Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF). Lakes, rivers, and reservoirs are critical for biodiversity, providing habitat for freshwater species, supporting ecosystem services such as water supply and carbon storage, and sustaining livelihoods. The FEI provides a globally harmonized, scientifically robust, and policy-relevant means of tracking phosphorus and nitrogen pollution in inland waters, two of the most pervasive drivers of freshwater degradation and biodiversity loss that are currently not captured by any existing GBF headline indicator for freshwater systems. While there is an existing indicator for coastal degradation that assesses nutrient impacts in coastal waters, this proposal now introduces the FEI specifically to address inland waters. By directly addressing nutrient pressures, the FEI supports GBF Target 7 (reducing pollution to levels not harmful to biodiversity) and Goal B (reducing threats to biodiversity), while also contributing to Targets 2, 3, and 8 on ecosystem restoration, area-based conservation, and ecological health. It aligns closely with SDG Indicator 6.3.2 on ambient water quality, allowing countries to make use of existing monitoring frameworks and data sources for GBF reporting and assessment.

The FEI operates through a three-tiered approach.

- **Level 1 – Globally modelled nutrient emissions:** Estimated anthropogenic phosphorus and nitrogen loads to surface water catchments, derived from global or regional models that account for land use, population, hydrology, and pollution inputs. These modelled data provide a baseline assessment of eutrophication risk, particularly in regions where in situ monitoring is limited.
- **Level 2 – Nutrient concentrations and management response:** National or local in situ monitoring of phosphorus, nitrogen, and chlorophyll concentrations in surface waters, combined with flow data to allow nutrient load calculations. Data are analysed using ISO 6878 or APHA methods. Where available, this tier allows estimation of the proportion of surface water catchments exceeding eutrophication thresholds and the proportion where nutrient action plans are active. Level 2 data also provide an opportunity to validate Level 1 estimates and can act as a catalyst for further national monitoring, helping countries identify priority waterbodies for additional data collection or management interventions.
- **Level 3 – Biological response:** Quantifies the proportion of surface water catchments showing symptoms of eutrophication, such as excessive algal growth. Remote sensing products, including Sentinel-2 (Lake Water Quality) and MODIS (chlorophyll-a, turbidity), are used to assess chlorophyll-a levels, turbidity, and observed algal blooms. This layer captures the ecological consequences of nutrient enrichment and provides insight into how other factors, including climate change, may influence eutrophication thresholds.

Together, the three levels offer flexible implementation: where only Levels 1 and 3 data are available, eutrophication risk can still be estimated reliably, while Level 2 data, when available, can validate and refine results.

The FEI has been developed to meet the criteria for GBF headline indicators under Decision 15/5 (Annex I). It draws primarily from open and reproducible data sources, applies peer-reviewed and UNEP-endorsed methods, and can be supported by UNEP and GEMS/Water with guidance and tools provided through the GEF/UNEP uPcycle project. The indicator enables temporal trend detection from 1990 onwards and aligns with existing global reporting processes, including the SDGs, the Ramsar Convention, UNEA resolutions on nutrient management, and the Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs) framework.

By combining modelled, observed, and remotely sensed information within a single coherent framework, the FEI provides a cost-effective, scalable, and policy-actionable solution for monitoring nutrient pollution and eutrophication risk. It bridges the gap between biodiversity and water-quality monitoring, strengthens coherence across environmental policy domains, and supports evidence-based action toward the 2030 GBF and SDG targets.

The following document presents the full proposal and includes an accompanying indicator fact sheet, which follows the standardized format and headings used for existing headline indicators under the KM-GBF.

This proposal has been developed and peer-reviewed through collaboration with a wide range of experts across regions, countries, and disciplines. It is submitted as a proposal rather than a final product and will be further refined and developed in consultation with Member States and through the broader processes established under the GBF.

Full Proposal

1. Indicator Name

The Freshwater Eutrophication Index (FEI)

2. Purpose and Relevance

Nutrient pollution is one of the leading pressures on freshwater ecosystems, driving widespread eutrophication and biodiversity loss (Brownlie et al., 2022). Currently, no GBF headline indicator estimates nutrient (phosphorus and nitrogen) pollution to inland freshwater bodies. The FEI fills this gap by providing a globally harmonized, scientifically robust measure of eutrophication risk.

By 2030, GBF Target 7 aims to cut excess nutrient losses by at least 50%. The FEI directly supports GBF Target 7 (reducing pollution to levels not harmful to biodiversity) and Goal B (sustainable use and benefit-sharing of biodiversity). It also complements other targets, including Target 2 (restoration), Target 3 (area-based conservation), and Target 8 (ecosystem health).

Aligned with ‘SDG Indicator 6.3.2 thresholds for good ambient water quality’¹, the FEI allows member states to repurpose collected data for national monitoring and reporting. It also contributes to broader international initiatives, including SDGs 6.3.2, 6.6.1, and 14.1.1, the UN Decade on Ecosystem Restoration, and UNEA resolutions on sustainable nutrient management and water quality.

3. Gap(s) Addressed

Although nutrient pollution is a major driver of freshwater biodiversity loss, the current GBF monitoring framework does not include a dedicated headline indicator for inland waters. As a result, there is no mechanism to quantify nutrient pressures or their direct impacts, such as excessive algal growth, which may limit countries’ ability to track progress on pollution reduction and ecosystem restoration objectives.

Key gaps addressed by FEI:

- Lack of a standardized global indicator for freshwater eutrophication, limiting comparability across countries and regions.
- Inadequate integration of nutrient pollution into biodiversity frameworks, which hinders coordinated management of pressures on freshwater ecosystems.
- Limited policy tools to support eutrophication risk assessment and nutrient reduction strategies, reducing the ability of governments to prioritize actions.
- Sparse or inconsistent nutrient and algal monitoring, particularly in developing regions, creating gaps in data availability for trend detection and policy decision-making.

4. Description of the Indicator

- The FEI estimates the eutrophication risk in lakes, rivers, and reservoirs by combining:

¹ Under SDG Indicator 6.3.2 (Proportion of bodies of water with good ambient water quality), nutrient status is assessed for surface waters through measurements of nitrogen and phosphorus against nationally defined thresholds. A water body is considered to have “good” nutrient status when at least 80% of monitoring results meet these standards. Threshold values are set by each country based on environmental, ecological, and human health considerations.

- **Nutrient emissions:** Estimated anthropogenic phosphorus and nitrogen loads to surface water catchments, derived from global or regional models that account for land use, population, hydrology, and pollution inputs.
- **Nutrient concentrations and management response:** Observed nutrient concentrations and loads from in situ monitoring, where available (e.g., national agencies, GEMS/Water, FAO AQUASTAT). This tier also allows calculation of the proportion of surface water catchments exceeding eutrophication thresholds and the proportion where nutrient management or action plans are active.
- **Biological response:** The proportion of surface water catchments showing symptoms of eutrophication, such as excessive algal growth. This is quantified using remote sensing products (e.g., Sentinel-2, MODIS) to measure chlorophyll-a levels, turbidity, or observed algal blooms, capturing the ecological consequences of nutrient enrichment.

5. Alignment with Criteria for Headline Indicators (Decision 15/5, Annex I)

Criteria	How the Proposed Indicator Meets the Criterion
(a) Publicly available data and metadata	The FEI draws primarily on publicly accessible data sources, including UNEP GEMS/Water, EEA, Copernicus Land Monitoring Service (Lake Water Quality), national databases, and global models. Data will be published via UNEP platforms and the GEF/UNEP uPcycle project data portal, ensuring open access beyond the life of the project.
(b) Methodology published or peer-reviewed	The FEI methodology is based on peer-reviewed models and validated approaches. It will be documented and published through UNEP to ensure transparency and reproducibility.
(c) Regularly updated data	Modelled data (Level 1) will be updated every 4–5 years, while in situ monitoring data (Level 2) will be updated every 1–3 years, aligned with the SDG 6.3.2 reporting cycle. Remote sensing data (Level 3) can also be regularly updated, depending on data source availability.
(d) Mechanism for maintenance	Maintenance and reporting can be supported by UNEP and GEMS/Water, with guidance and tools provided through the GEF/UNEP uPcycle project. Updates and technical support will leverage existing institutional frameworks.
(e) Ability to detect trends	The FEI allows temporal disaggregation and supports historical and future trend analysis, covering the period from 1990 onward. It can detect both improvements and deteriorations in nutrient emissions, concentrations, and eutrophication risk across multiple scales. The biological response component also enables observation of how other factors, including climate change, influence thresholds for algal blooms and overall eutrophication dynamics.
(f) Alignment with existing processes	The indicator is fully aligned with global reporting frameworks, including SDG 6.3.2 (“Proportion of bodies of water with good ambient water quality”), the Ramsar Convention, UNEA resolutions on nutrient management, and the Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs) framework. It is also compatible with regional and intergovernmental frameworks addressing nutrient pollution and freshwater quality, including: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU Water Framework Directive (Europe) • Great Lakes Water Quality Agreement (Canada–US) • Helsinki Commission (HELCOM) Baltic Sea Action Plan (Northern Europe) • Regional programs in Australasia (e.g., Australia’s National Water Quality Management Strategy). • China’s Environmental Quality Standards for Surface Water (GB3838-2002)

6. Methodology

FEI uses a three-tiered approach:

- **Level 1 – Globally modelled nutrient emissions:** Estimated anthropogenic phosphorus and nitrogen loads to surface water catchments², derived from global or regional models that account for land use, population, hydrology, and pollution inputs. These modelled data provide a baseline assessment of eutrophication risk, particularly in regions where in situ monitoring is limited.
- **Level 2 – Nutrient concentrations and management response:** National or local in situ monitoring of phosphorus, nitrogen, and chlorophyll concentrations in surface waters, combined with flow data to allow nutrient load calculations. Data are analysed using ISO 6878 or APHA methods. Where available, this tier allows estimation of the proportion of surface water catchments exceeding eutrophication thresholds and the proportion where nutrient action plans are active. Level 2 data also provide an opportunity to validate Level 1 estimates and can act as a catalyst for further national monitoring, helping countries identify priority waterbodies for additional data collection or management interventions.
- **Level 3 – Biological response:** Quantifies the proportion of surface water catchments showing symptoms of eutrophication³, such as excessive algal growth. Remote sensing products, including Sentinel-2 (Lake Water Quality) and MODIS (chlorophyll-a, turbidity), are used to assess chlorophyll-a levels, turbidity, and observed algal blooms. This layer captures the ecological consequences of nutrient enrichment and provides insight into how other factors, including climate change, may influence eutrophication thresholds.

Observed in situ data, where available, can be used to validate and calibrate both models and remotely-sensed data. The indicator reflects nutrient and chlorophyll concentrations relative to ecological thresholds, enabling risk-based categorization.

Additional implementation notes:

- **Disaggregation:** FEI results can be broken down by country, basin, or catchment and track both point and diffuse pollution sources, including groundwater.
- **Temporal coverage:** Supports trend analysis from 1990 onwards and allows monitoring at multiple spatial scales.
- **Flexibility:** Where full three-tiered data are unavailable, the FEI can be applied using only emissions or concentration data as proxies. Inclusion of the biological response, even in limited form, strengthens the ability of the indicator to reflect true eutrophication dynamics and biodiversity impacts.
- **Integration:** Builds on existing national and international monitoring programs to provide regular, scalable, and scientifically comparable data.

7. Proposed Data Sources

- **Global models:** IMAGE-GNM, MARINA, SPARROW, Global NEWS-2.

² Nutrient loads (phosphorus and nitrogen inputs from anthropogenic sources) are used to estimate pressures at the catchment scale, while nutrient concentrations in receiving waters reflect the realized state of those pressures. Combining these dimensions allows the FEI to capture both the drivers and outcomes of nutrient enrichment.

³ For the purposes of the FEI, eutrophication is defined as nutrient enrichment leading to measurable changes in ecosystem structure and function, including but not limited to excessive algal growth. This definition aligns with the original concept (Naumann, 1919) while incorporating contemporary understanding of biodiversity impacts.

- **Catchment models:** HydroGeoSphere
- **In situ monitoring:** National environmental agencies, GEMS/Water, FAO AQUASTAT.
- **Remote sensing:** Sentinel-2 (Lake Water Quality), MODIS (chlorophyll-a, turbidity).
- **Transboundary initiatives:** ICPDR, Nile Basin Initiative, Mekong River Commission.

8. Reporting and Update Mechanism

- **Lead Reporting Body:** UNEP, through GEMS/Water or similar initiatives
- **National Reporting:** Countries submit in situ data through established reporting systems or FEI mechanisms.
- **Update Frequency:** Modelled data updated every 4–5 years; in situ data every 1-3 years aligned with SDG 6.3.2 cycle.
- **Integration:** Outputs may feed into the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), and Biodiversity Indicators Partnership (BIP) reporting frameworks, to be decided in coordination with member states and relevant bodies.

9. Benefits

The Freshwater Eutrophication Index (FEI) provides a globally relevant, science-based, and policy-actionable indicator of nutrient pressures on freshwater ecosystems, addressing a major anthropogenic threat to biodiversity. It directly supports multiple GBF targets (particularly Targets 2, 3, 7, and 8) and Goal B, while aligning with global reporting frameworks such as the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), including SDG Indicator 6.3.2 on ambient water quality, the Ramsar Convention, the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), UNEA resolutions, and Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs).

The FEI enables consistent tracking of nutrient pollution and its ecological impacts across countries, supports national and sub-national trend analysis, and identifies priority areas for intervention, including hotspots of algal blooms. By integrating modelled, remotely sensed, and in situ data, it provides cost-effective, scalable, and evidence-based insights that guide policy development, restoration planning, and resource allocation. Its use of existing monitoring infrastructure and alignment with SDG 6.3.2 helps avoid duplication, ensures data comparability, and fosters coordinated reporting.

The indicator also strengthens coordination across water, climate, and biodiversity policies, promotes integration of water quality into biodiversity management, and encourages the enhancement of national monitoring capacities. By leveraging existing programs and initiatives, the FEI delivers co-benefits across biodiversity, water quality, human health, and sustainable development objectives.

Indicator Factsheet

1. Indicator name

Freshwater Eutrophication Index (FEI)

2. Date of metadata update

N/A

3. Goals and Targets addressed

The Freshwater Eutrophication Index (FEI) supports the implementation and monitoring of key global frameworks aimed at restoring ecosystems, protecting biodiversity, and improving water quality.

Under the **Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (GBF)**, the FEI contributes to:

- **Goal B:** Promotes the sustainable use and restoration of freshwater ecosystems by addressing nutrient pollution, a major driver of biodiversity loss.
- **Target 7:** Supports efforts to halve excess nutrient losses by 2030 through regular monitoring of phosphorus and nitrogen.
- **Target 2:** Informs restoration of degraded inland waters, where reducing eutrophication is essential for ecosystem recovery.
- **Target 3:** Enables effective conservation of freshwater bodies by tracking eutrophication status.
- **Target 8:** Contributes to climate resilience by supporting ecosystem-based approaches to maintain healthy freshwater systems.

In support of the **2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development**, FEI aligns especially with:

- **SDG 6.3:** Provides indicators to assess nutrient pollution reductions in freshwater, central to water quality improvements.
- **SDG 14:** Addresses inland nutrient sources contributing to coastal eutrophication.
- **SDG 15:** Supports protection of freshwater biodiversity as part of terrestrial ecosystems.
- **SDG 2 and SDG 12:** Promotes sustainable nutrient use in agriculture and industry.

The FEI also responds to key **UNEA Resolutions**, including:

- **Resolution 5/4** (Sustainable Lake Management)
- **Resolution 3/10** (Water Pollution)
- **Resolutions 4/14 and 4/2** (Nitrogen Management)
These emphasize the need for improved nutrient monitoring and data tools—functions directly addressed by the FEI.
- **Resolution 6/13.** Effective and inclusive solutions for strengthening water policies to achieve sustainable development in the context of climate change, biodiversity loss and pollution.

Additionally, the FEI contributes to:

- **UN Resolution A/HRC/RES/48/13:** Supporting the right to a clean, healthy, and sustainable environment by tracking eutrophication threats.

- **UN Decade on Ecosystem Restoration (2021–2030):** Guiding restoration of nutrient-impaired freshwater ecosystems through actionable data.

4. Influential Regional and National Policies

Influential Regional and National Policies Supporting Eutrophication Control

- **EU Water Framework Directive**
Requires all EU water bodies to achieve “good status,” including safe nutrient levels and limited development of algal blooms; widely seen as a model for integrated water management.
- **US Clean Water Act**
Sets legal standards for pollution control; includes nutrient management through Total Maximum Daily Load (TMDL) programmes.
- **China’s Water Pollution Prevention and Control Action Plan**
Targets nutrient reductions in major rivers and lakes; demonstrates a strong national commitment to controlling eutrophication.
- **Other intergovernmental or regional frameworks** addressing nutrient pollution and freshwater quality (non-inclusive), including:
 - Great Lakes Water Quality Agreement (Canada–US)
 - Helsinki Commission (HELCOM) Baltic Sea Action Plan (Northern Europe)
 - Regional programs in Australasia (e.g., Australia’s National Water Quality Management Strategy).
 - China’s Environmental Quality Standards for Surface Water (GB3838-2002)

4. Rationale

Lakes, rivers, and reservoirs are critical for biodiversity, providing habitat for freshwater species, supporting ecosystem services such as water supply and carbon storage, and sustaining livelihoods (WWQA Ecosystems, 2023). Inland waters (i.e. rivers, lakes, and reservoirs), are highly sensitive to nutrient pollution, particularly excess phosphorus, which is the primary driver of eutrophication in many freshwater systems (Johnes et al., 2022; WWQA Ecosystems, 2023). Nitrogen also plays a critical role, especially in nitrogen-limited ecosystems and when transported downstream to estuaries and coastal waters (Conley et al., 2009; Sutton et al., 2013). Algal blooms are recognised as a widespread symptom of excessive nutrient pollution in lakes and reservoirs affecting the quality of water supply, water use and biodiversity.

Excess nutrients mainly comes from agricultural runoff and poorly managed wastewater (Beusen et al., 2016; Bouwman et al., 2009; Seitzinger et al., 2010). When it enters freshwater bodies, it triggers harmful algal blooms that, upon decay, deplete oxygen, kill fish, disrupt aquaculture, and render drinking water unsafe. In extreme cases, this pollution makes water bodies unusable for both people and wildlife. Over 83% of freshwater habitats in the EU were classed as being in an unfavourable condition in 2015, higher than any other habitat type (European Environment Agency, 2015), many of which are impacted by eutrophication. Nutrient enrichment changes ecosystems and can have major impact on the services that surface and groundwaters provide to humans and lead to significant detrimental effects on inland and coastal biodiversity (UNEP, 2016).

But the effects of inland nutrient pollution do not stop at the water’s edge. Much of the excess phosphorus and nitrogen eventually flows downstream into coastal waters, fuelling eutrophication symptoms of algal blooms in estuaries and oceans. In more extreme, but not uncommon, situations this cascade contributes to the formation of vast hypoxic “dead zones” such as those in the Baltic Sea, Gulf of Mexico, and Chesapeake Bay—regions where oxygen levels are too low to support marine life (Johnes et al., 2022). These coastal crises are emblematic of a broader global issue: if nutrient

pollution remains unaddressed, the resulting biodiversity loss could become irreversible, threatening ecosystems that support human well-being and planetary health (Carpenter & Bennett, 2011; WWQA Ecosystems, 2023).

To tackle this problem effectively, countries need tools to track and manage nutrient pollution from source to sea. The proposed '**Freshwater Eutrophication Index (FEI)**' provides a standardized, scalable measure of eutrophication risk in inland waters. It combines terrestrial nutrient input data (e.g., from agriculture, wastewater) with in situ water quality monitoring to assess phosphorus and nitrogen loads and algal concentrations to identify pollution "hotspots" and risks to biodiversity and human health.

By enabling consistent tracking of inland water quality trends, FEI supports national efforts to reduce pollution, protect biodiversity, and prevent downstream impacts on coastal and marine ecosystems. It is a vital step toward integrated, science-based management of the entire aquatic continuum—from headwaters to ocean.

5. Definitions, concepts and classifications

5a. Definition

The FEI measures the potential for eutrophication in inland waters based on phosphorus and nitrogen inputs from terrestrial sources, supported by in situ measurements of lake nutrient and algal concentrations. It integrates both modelled nutrient loads and observed water quality data where available.

Unit of measure:

- Phosphorus load per square kilometre of watershed area per year ($\text{kg P km}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$).
- Nitrogen load per square kilometre of watershed area per year ($\text{kg N km}^{-2} \text{ yr}^{-1}$).
- Phosphorus concentrations in lake water of monitored site ($\mu\text{g P L}^{-1}$)
- Nitrogen concentrations in lakes, if data are available (mg N L^{-1})
- Algal concentrations in lakes and reservoirs, if data are available ($\mu\text{g Chlorophyll-a L}^{-1}$)

5b. Method of computation

Level 1 – Globally modelled nutrient emissions

Estimated anthropogenic phosphorus and nitrogen loads to surface water catchments are derived from global or regional models that account for land use, population, hydrology, and pollution inputs. These modelled data provide a baseline assessment of eutrophication risk, particularly in regions where in situ monitoring is limited.

Estimates of nutrient loading are generated from spatially explicit models that integrate land use, fertilizer application, wastewater inputs, population density, and hydrological characteristics. Relevant models include:

- **IMAGE-GNM**⁴ (Beusen et al., 2015, 2016): A global model developed by PBL Netherlands that simulates nitrogen and phosphorus export from terrestrial systems to surface waters and coastal zones. *Suitable for national-scale assessments; application requires technical capacity and access to global input datasets.*
- **MARINA**⁵ (Strokal et al., 2016): A basin-scale model developed by Wageningen University and the Chinese Academy of Sciences that quantifies nutrient inputs, river export, and source attribution across over 600 global basins. *Effective for regional and global analyses; local calibration may be necessary for country-level detail.*
- **SPARROW**⁶ (Hoos & McMahon, 2009; Kim et al., 2017; Schwarz et al., 2011): A modelling framework from the U.S. Geological Survey that estimates nutrient sources, transport, and fate based on statistical relationships with watershed attributes and observed water quality. *Adaptable for national or sub-national contexts where sufficient monitoring and spatial data are available.*
- **Global NEWS-2**⁷ (Mayorga et al., 2010; Seitzinger et al., 2010): A global, spatially explicit model developed by the International Geosphere-Biosphere Programme (IGBP) and the Global Nutrient Export from WaterSheds (NEWS) consortium. It estimates the export of nutrients, including nitrogen and phosphorus, from watersheds to coastal waters. NEWS-2 is freely available. *Suitable for global and regional assessments and requires technical capacity to access and process input datasets such as land use, population, fertilizer application, sewage treatment, hydrology, and dam retention.*

Level 2 – Nutrient concentrations and management response

National or local in situ monitoring of phosphorus, nitrogen, and chlorophyll concentrations in surface waters, combined with flow data, allows for nutrient load calculations. Data are analysed using ISO 6878 or APHA methods. Where available, this tier enables estimation of the proportion of surface

⁴ IMAGE-GNM (Integrated Model to Assess the Global Environment – Global Nutrient Model) is a global nutrient modelling framework developed by the PBL Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency. It estimates nitrogen and phosphorus export from watersheds to surface waters and coasts by simulating nutrient flows from land-based sources (agriculture, wastewater, atmospheric deposition) through hydrological pathways, supporting assessments of pollution impacts on freshwater and marine ecosystems.

⁵ MARINA (Model to Assess River Inputs of Nutrients to seAs) is a global, basin-scale nutrient modelling framework developed by Wageningen University & Research (WUR) and the Chinese Academy of Sciences. It quantifies nitrogen and phosphorus inputs from human activities (e.g. agriculture, wastewater, aquaculture) and estimates their transport and export through river systems to coastal waters. MARINA supports assessments of nutrient pollution, source attribution, and future scenarios across over 600 major river basins worldwide, helping evaluate impacts on both freshwater and marine ecosystems.

⁶ SPARROW (SPATIally Referenced Regressions On Watershed Attributes), developed by the U.S. Geological Survey (USGS), is a regional-scale modelling framework that estimates the origin, transport, and fate of nutrients and other pollutants in river systems using statistical relationships between observed water quality and spatial watershed characteristics.

⁷ Global NEWS-2 provides a detailed assessment of nutrient sources, transport, and delivery to coastal systems. It distinguishes between dissolved and particulate forms of nutrients and accounts for human activities (agriculture, wastewater, atmospheric deposition) and natural processes influencing nutrient retention and flux. The model supports scenario analysis, source attribution, and evaluation of nutrient management policies, enabling assessment of nutrient pressures on both freshwater and marine ecosystems.

water catchments exceeding eutrophication thresholds and the proportion where nutrient action plans are active. Level 2 data also provide an opportunity to validate Level 1 estimates and can act as a catalyst for further national monitoring, helping countries identify priority waterbodies for additional data collection or management interventions.

At Level 2, countries refine eutrophication risk assessments using in situ monitoring data at national, basin, and catchment scales. These datasets allow for assessments that reflect local environmental conditions, pollution sources, and management priorities. While global models (Level 1) provide broad spatial coverage, Level 2 enables more targeted planning and progress tracking.

Examples of regional and international data sources and coordination efforts include:

- UNEP GEMS/Water: A global platform compiling national water quality monitoring data from government and institutional sources (see: <https://gemstat.org/data-gemstat/data-portal>).
- European Environment Agency (EEA): Manages the WISE database under the EU Water Framework Directive, with harmonised nutrient and chlorophyll-a monitoring data from member states.
- United States: The National Water Quality Monitoring Council supports data sharing through platforms like WQX, covering nutrient concentrations, chlorophyll-a and flow data.
- Hydrological data sources include global river flow and discharge datasets, such as the Global Flood Awareness System (GloFAS), GEOGLOWS retrospective flow data for global catchments, and planned datasets from applications such as HydroLand.

Transboundary basin monitoring:

- Danube – coordinated by the ICPDR
- Nile Basin – through the Nile Basin Initiative
- Mekong River – via the Mekong River Commission

Remote sensing technologies (e.g. Sentinel-2, MODIS) are also increasingly used to support or validate ground-based monitoring, particularly where regular field data are lacking. In particular, The European Copernicus Land Monitoring Service (Sentinel 2-MSI & Sentinel 3-OLCI – see https://land.copernicus.eu/en/products/water-bodies?tab=lake_water_quality) provides open-access global coverage of chlorophyll-a levels for a large number of medium and large-sized lakes every 10 days since 2024. Additional chlorophyll-a data products are available from other national space agencies.

In combination, local, national or regional scale monitoring efforts are essential for countries to prioritise interventions, track nutrient reduction goals, and report progress towards targets such as SDG 6.3.2.

Level 3 – Biological response

Level 3 quantifies the proportion of surface water catchments showing symptoms of eutrophication—such as excessive algal growth—using remote sensing and biological observation. Remote sensing products, including Sentinel-2 (Lake Water Quality) and MODIS (chlorophyll-a, turbidity), are used to assess chlorophyll-a levels, turbidity, and observed algal blooms. This layer captures the ecological consequences of nutrient enrichment and provides insight into how other factors, including climate change, may influence eutrophication thresholds.

The biological response to nutrient enrichment is assessed through indicators of eutrophication symptoms, primarily excessive algal growth, chlorophyll-a concentration, and turbidity. This tier

represents the ecological outcome of nutrient pressures rather than the pressures themselves, providing direct evidence of how nutrient loading affects freshwater ecosystem health.

The FEI integrates satellite-based remote sensing, field-based biological observations, and, where available, ecological status assessments from national monitoring programmes. Remote sensing enables consistent, repeatable, and large-scale observations of water quality parameters that are difficult or costly to obtain through field sampling alone.

Remote sensing sources and products:

- **Copernicus Sentinel-2 MSI and Sentinel-3 OLCI:** Provide open-access global coverage of chlorophyll-a, turbidity, and surface reflectance in lakes and reservoirs at spatial resolutions of 10–300 m, updated approximately every 10 days since 2024.
- **MODIS (Terra and Aqua):** Offers complementary chlorophyll-a and turbidity estimates with long-term global coverage since 2000, enabling historical trend analysis and validation of Sentinel-based products.
- **Landsat (NASA/USGS):** Provides a long-term time series (since the 1980s) suitable for retrospective analysis of eutrophication trends at coarser temporal resolution.
- **National or regional satellite programmes** (e.g. CONAE in Argentina, INPE in Brazil) may supply higher-resolution or locally tailored products.

These datasets are processed using established bio-optical algorithms that convert spectral reflectance to chlorophyll-a and turbidity estimates. Outputs allow identification of areas exhibiting persistent or seasonal algal blooms and provide spatially explicit information on the intensity and extent of eutrophication.

Integration with ecological and climatic data: Where available, in situ chlorophyll-a, phytoplankton, and macrophyte observations from national monitoring programmes or initiatives like GEMS/Water are used to validate and calibrate satellite-derived estimates. Level 3 also enables examination of climate interactions, as rising temperatures and altered hydrological regimes influence bloom frequency, duration, and severity. These data can be combined with Levels 1 and 2 to identify catchments where climatic drivers may amplify nutrient-related risks.

Relevance and application: The Level 3 layer provides the biological expression of eutrophication and supports risk classification according to ecological thresholds. By mapping bloom frequency and intensity over time, it enables detection of improvements or deteriorations in water quality and ecosystem condition. This tier is particularly valuable for countries lacking dense in situ networks, as it offers near-global coverage and supports cost-effective national reporting aligned with SDG Indicator 6.3.2 and GBF Target 7.

5c. Data collection method

- Global baseline data are generated using remote sensing and spatially explicit hydrological models.
- National environmental agencies collect phosphorus and nitrogen concentrations and loads and chlorophyll-a concentrations through routine monitoring of rivers, lakes, and reservoirs.
- Citizen science and indigenous community-based monitoring can complement official data collection. Citizen science of harmful algal blooms is widespread in USA and expanding across Europe.

5d. Accessibility of methodology

The FEI computation methodology will be published in peer-reviewed literature and disseminated through UNEP-led initiatives such as the GEF/UNEP uPcycle project and other international water quality assessment platforms as appropriate.

5e. Data sources

- UNEP GEMS/Water Programme
- GEF/UNEP uPcycle project data portal
- FAO AQUASTAT
- Global NEWS-2, IMAGE-GNM, MARINA, and SPARROW models
- Copernicus Land Monitoring Service (Sentinel 2-MSI & Sentinel 3-OLCI)
- National environmental and hydrological monitoring programmes

5f. Availability and release calendar

- Global modelled FEI outputs updated every 4–5 years
- National-level data updates recommended every 1-3 years to align with SDG 6.3.2 reporting cycles

5g. Time series

- Modelled nutrient loading data available from 1990 onwards
- National monitoring records vary; some countries maintain continuous data since the 1990s.

5h. Examples of Data providers

- UNEP GEMS/Water
- Copernicus Land Monitoring Service (Sentinel 2-MSI & Sentinel 3-OLCI)
- Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO)
- National water quality monitoring agencies and institutions

5i. Data compilers

- UNEP, in collaboration with the Global Water Partnership (GWP), scientific experts, and academic institutions, could support coordination and technical guidance for FEI implementation.
- Member States would remain the primary data compilers and custodians, responsible for national-level FEI assessments, reporting, and data submissions.
- The uPcycle project will provide openly accessible guidance materials, tools, and data resources to enable countries to independently run their own FEI assessments using globally harmonized methods.
- Technical inputs for modelled components (Level 1) could be drawn from existing global nutrient emission models maintained by partners such as PBL Netherlands (IMAGE-GNM), Wageningen University (MARINA), and the USGS (SPARROW).
- Remote sensing inputs (Level 3) could be supported through collaboration with the European Space Agency (ESA), NASA, and national space agencies to ensure consistent global data access.

5j. Gaps in data coverage

- In-situ water quality monitoring remains limited in many regions, particularly in parts of Africa, Asia, and Latin America, where monitoring networks are sparse or irregular.
- Remote and transboundary watersheds often lack consistent long-term datasets or harmonized sampling protocols.
- Existing programmes may emphasize physical parameters (e.g., temperature, flow) rather than nutrient and biological indicators needed for eutrophication assessment.
- Historical or legacy datasets may exist but be inaccessible due to data ownership, non-digitized formats, or absence of data-sharing mechanisms.
- Gaps in ancillary data, such as fertilizer application rates, wastewater discharge, and land use may affect model accuracy.

Addressing these gaps could be supported through targeted capacity development, strengthening national monitoring systems and improving integration between in situ, modelled, and remotely sensed data sources.

5k. Treatment of missing values

Missing data in national in situ monitoring datasets (e.g., nutrient concentrations or loads) would not be statistically interpolated or filled. Spatial or temporal gaps could instead be complemented using model-based estimates or remote sensing products, which would be clearly identified as distinct from measured data in metadata and outputs. Documented data gaps should be recorded to guide national monitoring investments and capacity-building priorities.

Uncertainty treatment: Each FEI component (Levels 1–3) includes inherent uncertainty due to model assumptions, data variability, and measurement limitations. To manage this:

- Uncertainty ranges or confidence intervals could be estimated for key parameters such as nutrient loads and chlorophyll-a concentrations.
- FEI results exceeding agreed uncertainty thresholds could be flagged and, where necessary, excluded from aggregate or trend analyses until validated.
- Metadata accompanying FEI outputs should describe the main uncertainty sources (e.g., data origin, spatial resolution, calibration, and validation method).
- Regular cross-validation between modelled, remote sensing, and in situ datasets could be used to quantify and reduce uncertainty over time.

Duplicate and outlier management: Because multiple data sources may overlap, a harmonisation and validation protocol could be applied to manage duplicates and outliers:

- Preference could be given to official national submissions with recognised QA/QC procedures.
- Duplicates may be identified through site identifiers, coordinates, and sampling dates, with the most recent or verified dataset retained for analysis.
- Outliers (e.g., extreme or implausible nutrient values) could be flagged through standard QA/QC methods and reviewed before exclusion.
- Comparison against modelled or satellite-based data could help confirm or correct anomalous values.

Documentation and reporting: A data quality and uncertainty protocol could accompany all national and global FEI datasets to ensure transparency and comparability. Countries could include metadata on data quality, sampling frequency, analytical methods, and QA/QC procedures when submitting FEI data through UNEP or other reporting mechanisms. UNEP and partners could provide open-access training and technical support through the uPcycle initiative, enabling member states to run their own assessments using consistent data management and uncertainty evaluation methods.

6. Scale

6a. Scale of use

- Global, regional, national, sub-national watershed and lake levels.
- FEI can be reported at the basin scale and aggregated nationally.

6b. National/regional indicator production

- Countries can use existing national monitoring systems and datasets to calculate and report FEI values, building on their own water quality networks and analytical capacity.
- Guidance, tools, and training resources for national FEI calculation will be made available through UNEP GEMS/Water (and GEF/UNEP uPcycle project), ensuring countries can independently undertake assessments.
- Model-based or remote sensing data will be used to complement national data where in situ measurements are unavailable, with clear identification of these data types in metadata and reporting outputs. The extent of model data coverage will depend on national data availability and model applicability.

6c. Sources of differences between global and national figures

- Global estimates are model-based and harmonized (e.g. validated against those regions where measurements exist); national figures are derived from direct measurements.
- Variability arises from monitoring frequency, sampling locations and methods.

6d. Regional and global estimates & data collection for global monitoring

6d.1 Description of the methodology

- Global modelled datasets calibrated and validated with available in situ measurements.
- National data integrated into the global dataset where available.

6d.2 Additional methodological details

- Statistical models account for natural phosphorus, nitrogen and chlorophyll-a background levels to avoid overestimation in pristine systems.

6d.3 Description of the mechanism for collecting data from countries

- National environmental agencies and water authorities would be the primary providers of in situ nutrient monitoring data, through existing national reporting frameworks or dedicated FEI submissions.
- Regional and transboundary river basin organizations (e.g. ICPDR, Nile Basin Initiative, Mekong River Commission) could facilitate coordinated data reporting across shared watersheds.
- UNEP GEMS/Water may serve as a central platform for compiling and harmonizing submitted data, especially where national submissions align with its existing datasets.
- Alternatively or additionally, [the GEF/UNEP uPcycle project](#), through its emerging monitoring and assessment framework and data portal, could host the FEI methodology and coordinate data collection, particularly during early implementation.
- Over time, integration with broader UN water reporting systems (e.g. for SDG 6.3.2) or partnerships with organizations like FAO, UNEP-WCMC, or UNESCO-IHP could be

explored to ensure alignment and sustainability.

7. Other MEAs, processes and organisations

7a. Other MEA and processes

- Sustainable Development Goals (SDG)
 - SDG 6.3.2 – Proportion of bodies of water with good ambient water quality.
 - SDG 6.6.1 – Change in the extent of water-related ecosystems over time.
 - SDG 14.1.1 – Index of coastal eutrophication and floating plastic debris density (linked to inland nutrient exports).
- Ramsar Convention on Wetlands – advocates water quality monitoring under the Wise Use concept and links to restoration of degraded wetlands.
- Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) – FEI directly supports implementation and monitoring of the Kunming-Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (particularly Targets 2, 3, 7, and 8 as discussed).
- UN Decade on Ecosystem Restoration (2021–2030) – FEI data supports prioritisation and tracking of freshwater ecosystem restoration efforts.
- UNEA Resolutions – Including Resolutions 5/4 (Sustainable Lake Management), 3/10 (Water Pollution), and 4/14 (Nitrogen Management).

7b. Biodiversity Indicator Partnership (BIP)

- Collaboration with BIP will support the integration of FEI into global biodiversity monitoring systems, and enable alignment with other indicators used under the GBF.
- The BIP can facilitate capacity-building and harmonisation of national-level reporting, especially for countries with limited monitoring infrastructure.
- FEI can complement existing BIP indicators related to ecosystem condition, freshwater integrity, and pollution pressure.

8. Disaggregation

- Geographic scale: Disaggregation at watershed and sub-watershed levels for policy-relevant granularity.
- Thematic disaggregation:
 - Phosphorus risk zones and nitrogen vulnerable zones based on FEI scoring thresholds.
 - Source attribution where models (e.g., MARINA, SPARROW) allow nutrient loading to be traced to sectors (agriculture, wastewater, atmospheric deposition).
- Administrative scale: Reporting by country, major river basin, or hydrological unit (e.g., HUCs or WFD catchments in EU context).
- Temporal disaggregation: Where time series data exist, allow assessment of trends and changes over time (e.g., pre- and post-intervention).

9. Related indicators

- SDG 6.3.2 – Ambient water quality (directly linked; FEI contributes nutrient-specific insights).
- SDG 6.6.1 – Change in extent of water-related ecosystems (eutrophication as a degradation driver).
- SDG 14.1.1 – Coastal eutrophication index (linked through nutrient export pathways).
- SDG 15.1.1 & 15.1.2 – Freshwater and terrestrial biodiversity indicators.
- Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs) – Especially those on biogeochemical flows,

- ecosystem functioning, and freshwater quality.
- UNEP Nitrogen Working Group indicators – FEI can contribute to global nitrogen assessments and indicators under nitrogen-use efficiency and environmental nitrogen losses.
- WRI Aqueduct and OECD water risk indicators – Potential for integration or alignment where nutrient pollution contributes to broader water risk profiles.

10. Data reporter

10a. Organisation

The United Nations Environment Programme (UNEP) is proposed as the lead data reporter for the FEI indicator, given its mandate on freshwater quality and global environmental monitoring. Reporting may be coordinated through relevant UNEP initiatives, such as the [GEF/UNEP uPcycle project](#) and in collaboration with UNEP's Science Division and the GEMS/Water Programme. Additional contributions and technical support may be provided by partner organisations including UNESCO, the Global Water Partnership (GWP), academic institutions, and regional bodies such as river basin organisations.

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